

CHARACTERISTICS OF INSULATING RESIN/INORGANIC COMPOSITES

D.S. Seo, M.J. Yoo, W.S. Lee, and S.D. Park*

Korea Electronics Technology Institute, Seongnam 463-816, Korea

* Corresponding author(sdpark@keti.re.kr)

Keywords: *Polyetherimide, Polyphenyleneether, inorganic filler, Film, Composite*

1 Introduction

Recently, issues in development of advanced semiconductor devices are miniaturization with high density and complex functionality of electronic products [1]. In the field of high density printed circuit board (PCB) for semiconductor package, patterned prepreg lay up process (PALAP) has been developed by Denso Corporation. PALAP is a printed circuit board fabrication process, and can easily make high-density and high-speed multi-layers in a short time [2].

The importance of engineering thermoplastics has been increased for use in electronics due to their good physical and dielectric properties. In PALAP process, polyether ether ketone (PEEK) and polyetherimide (PEI) blend, which both are high temperature thermoplastic materials, are mainly used. PEEK is a quite expensive material and consequently is only used in high technology applications such as aerospace materials [3].

Among thermoplastic polymers, polyphenylene ether (PPE) exhibits low moisture absorption, high glass transition temperature, low dielectric constant and dielectric loss over a wide temperature and frequency range, and high flame retardancy without the use of halogenated materials [4]. Polyetherimide, one of the polyimide families, has been attracted in microelectronic applications because of its low dielectric constant and low thermal expansion coefficient [5]. However, PEI and PPE show poor film-forming ability and low resistance to solder heat.

Inorganic ceramic materials have been used in the electronic packaging industries for a few decades [6]. Silica (SiO₂) filler especially has been added into the polymeric materials to reduce the coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) and improve the mechanical properties of the resins due to relatively low CTE and cost-effective processing [7].

In this study, PEI/PPE/SiO₂ composites were prepared by solution casting in which less expensive PPE than PPEK and cost-effective processing method are used. The effect of inorganic SiO₂ filler on the physical properties of the composites was investigated.

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials

Polyetherimide (PEI) was supplied by GE plastic, USA under the trade name Ultem1000. From the same supplier, two kinds of modified Polyphenyleneether (PPE) with the commercial name of PKN4752 and IC780 (Noryl resin) was obtained, denoted as PPE1 and PPE2, respectively. SiO₂ powder (SFP-30M by Denka, Japan) as an inorganic filler and a dispersant were used. *N,N'*-*m*-phenylene dimaleimide (PDMI, Sartomer, SR525) as a cross-linking agent and 1,3-bis(*tert*-butylperoxyisopropyl) benzene (Nippon Oil & Fats Co.) named Perbutyl P as an initiator were used. To prepare a resin solution, 1,2-dichloroethane (99%, SAMCHUN Chemical, Korea) was used.

2.2 Preparation of PEI-PPE-SiO₂ films

10-50 phr of SiO₂ powder (per hundred of PEI and PPE resin) was ball milled with a dispersant in 1,2-dichloroethane for 24 h to remove agglomerates and achieve homogeneity. The optimum dispersant concentrations were determined using settling experiments. The SiO₂ slurry was mixed with the solution of PEI and PPE in 1,2-dichloroethane with a concentration of 20 wt% by additional ball milling at ambient temperature for 24 h using zirconia ball media. The mixing ratio of PEI:PPE (in wt%) was 90:10, 70:30, 50:50, 30:70, 10:90. 20 wt% PDMI (based on the weight of PEI/PPE resin) and 5 wt% Perbutyl P (based on the weight of PDMI) were

added. Tape casting was performed using a tape-caster, by which slurry was coated on a polyethylene (PET) carrier film with a casting speed of 0.5 m/min at 60, 70 and 80°C. The thickness of the tapes so produced was about 70-80 μm .

2.3 Preparation of PEI-PPE-SiO₂ laminates

The stacked tapes (10 cm x 10 cm) with Cu foil ($t=12\ \mu\text{m}$) in a 20 cm x 20 cm stainless steel die were heated and compressed in a vacuum laminator, including two temperature ranges (160-190°C and 230-250°C), two levels of pressure (15 kg/cm² and 35 kg/cm²) and a holding time for 1 h. The thickness of the films after lamination ranged from 140-160 μm .

2.4 Analysis and characterization

The film/Cu foil adhesion strengths were determined using a tensile strength tester (Instron Model 5543). For the peel strength measurement, the sizes of the samples were kept at 1 cm wide and 6-7 cm long. The 90° peel test was conducted at a cross head speed of 20 mm/min. Dynamic mechanical analyses of the composites were done by a TA Instrument (Q800 model) in tension film mode. The storage modulus, loss modulus and $\tan\ \delta$ were recorded at a frequency of 1 Hz from ambient to 300°C and at a heating rate of 3°C/min. Water absorption is normally measured as weight gain in relation to initial total weight. A test piece in the form of 50 x 50 mm was immersed in distilled water at $23 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ for 24 h. For the measurement of the resistance to soldering heat, all copper foil on one side of a sample was removed and then a half of the copper foil of another side was removed. After the sample was put in the soldering bath at 288 °C for 10 seconds, check the copper foil surface and copper foil removed surface visually whether any blister or delamination exist or not.

3 Result and discussion

The peel strength of the laminated PEI/PPE1 composites with the mixing ratio of PEI and PPE1 is shown in Fig. 1. The overall adhesion strength between copper and the composite films was better than a commercial film, PEEK/PEI alloy (IBUKI, Mitsubishi Plastics). The adhesion strength of the composites increased when the cross-linking agent

Fig. 1. Peel strength of PEI/PPE1 composites.

was added. In addition, increasing the amount of the PEI seemed to improve the adhesion strength of the composite. This observation shows that the adhesion ability to copper foil can be improved by adding a cross-linking agent and changing the mixing ratio of PEI and PPE.

However, as presented in Fig. 2, storage modulus (E') of the PEI/PPE1 composites showed approximately 3,000-3,500 MPa, which is lower than the commercial film. As storage modulus is related to material's stiffness, the E' values of composites needs to be improved.

Moisture absorption is a critical parameter affecting the performance of a thermoplastic resin in micro-electronics [8].

Fig. 2. Storage modulus of PEI/PPE1 composites.

Table 1. Water absorption of PEI/PPE1 composites

Samples	Water absorbability (%)
9PEI1PPE1-Co	0.48
7PEI3PPE1-Co	0.44
5PEI5PPE1-Co	0.16
IBUKI	0.15

Table 1 shows the water absorption of PEI/PPE1 composites immersed in distilled water at 23°C for 24 h. The moisture absorption of the composites decreased with increasing the amount of PPE because of the low moisture absorption of PPE. It is generally known that a thermoplastic resin can be hydrolyzed by moisture, followed by degradation of physical properties of the resin such as glass transition temperature and coefficient of thermal expansion. The electrical insulating properties of the resin can be also decreased by the hydrolysis. It means that the composite requires low water absorption in electric applications. The water absorption of the 5PEI5PPE1 composite was as low as that of the commercial film.

The resistance of a thermoplastic-based resin to soldering heat is another important characteristic in advanced microelectronic packaging because heat resistance of the resin directly affects package performance and reliability [9]. We evaluated soldering heat resistance of the PEI/PPE1 composites and found that all compositions showed poor resistance to soldering heat, i.e. the presence of blister on the laminate surface and delamination between copper foil and laminates.

From the results of PEI/PPE1 composites, we focused on the preparation of resin composites with high mechanical property, good solder resistance and workability, i.e. film-forming ability by adding inorganic filler, SiO₂. In addition, as the 5PEI5PPE1 composite had good water resistance (Table 1), the mixing ratio of the following SiO₂-added PEI/PPE2 composite was fixed in 50:50 (wt %).

The film-forming ability of PEI/PPE2 was checked and presented in Fig. 3. PEI/PPE2 film without SiO₂ was warped showing low film formability similar to the cases of PEI/PPE1 samples. As SiO₂ was added, the film showed somewhat better film formability,

Fig. 3. Film-forming ability of PEI/PPE2 composites; (a) w/o SiO₂, (b) 10%SiO₂, (c) 30%SiO₂ and (d) 50%SiO₂.

and the PEI/PPE/30%SiO₂ system could form a film without cracks. However, the addition of 50%SiO₂ provided very brittle film with many cracks.

Fig. 4 shows peel strengths of the PEI/PPE2 composites with SiO₂ content. The overall adhesion strength between copper and the composite films was better than a commercial film, meaning that the PEI/PPE2 composites can be used as a printed circuit board material.

Fig. 5 shows storage modulus (E') of the composites with SiO₂ content. Dynamic mechanical analysis is a good method to determine the effects exerted by the filler on the resin matrix [10]. The incorporation of the ceramic filler causes an increase of the dynamic

Fig. 4. Peel strengths of PEI/PPE2 composites; (a) commercial, (b) w/o SiO₂, (c) 10%SiO₂, (d) 30%SiO₂ and (e) 50%SiO₂.

Fig. 5. Storage modulus of PEI/PPE2 composites.

storage modulus in all intervals of temperatures studied. The PEI/PPE2 composite without SiO₂ had the lowest E' value of about 2,500 MPa. By the addition of SiO₂ filler, the storage modulus of the composites increased up to about 5,000 MPa. Although the E' values of the composites were relatively lower than that of commercial film, DMA characteristics can be improved by controlling the amount of SiO₂ addition.

We also checked the resistance to soldering heat of the composites and presented in Table 2. The sample without SiO₂ was distorted and failed as soon as it was dipped in a soldering bath. As the amount of SiO₂ increased, the composites showed no change, i.e. either blister or delamination on their surfaces. It may be expected that the resin system with 30% of silica addition has compatible heat resistance to the commercial film with respect to film-forming ability.

Table 2. Heat resistance of PEI/PPE2 composites after dipping in solder bath at 288°C for 10s.

Samples	Heat resistance
PEI/PPE2	bad
10SiO ₂ PEI/PPE2	moderate
30SiO ₂ PEI/PPE2	good
50SiO ₂ PEI/PPE2	good

4 Conclusions

Thermoplastic polymer/ceramic hybrid materials were prepared by solution-casting process. The addition of silica improved physical properties of the PEI/PPE polymer, such as film-forming ability, storage modulus and the resistance to soldering heat. The PEI/PPE/SiO₂ system in this study can be an alternative substrate material in electronic devices.

Acknowledgement

This work was supported by the Technology Innovation Program funded by the Ministry of Knowledge Economy (MKE, Korea).

References

- [1] J.M. Show, "Overview of polymers for electronic and photonic applications". In: Wang CP, editor. *Polymers for electronic and photonic applications*. New York: Academic Press, 1993.
- [2] R. Kataoka, et al., "Semiconductor Packaging Technology Based on the PALAP Process". *Densu Technical Review*, 10(2), 77-84, 2005.
- [3] M.J. Jenkins, "Crystallisation in miscible blends of PEEK and PEI". *Polymer*, 42, 1981-86, 2001.
- [4] E. N. Peters, "Engineering Plastics Handbook Thermoplastics, Properties, and Applications". J. Margolis ed., McGraw-Hill, New York, 2005.
- [5] D.M. Delozier, et al., "Preparation and characterization of polyimide/organoclay nanocomposites". *Polymer*, 43, 813-22, 2002.
- [6] J. Kloeser, et al., "IEEE Transactions on Components, Packaging and Manufacturing Technology". Part A 24, 1996.
- [7] P.L. Teh, et al., "The properties of epoxy resin coated silica fillers composites". *Materials Letters*, 61, 2156-58, 2007.
- [8] F. Tan, et al., "Effects of coupling agents on the properties of epoxy-based electrically conductive adhesives". *International Journal of Adhesion & Adhesives*, 26, 406-13, 2006.
- [9] Y. Etoh, et al., "A study of soldering heat evaluation for SMDs". *Microelectronics Reliability*, 38, 1313-18, 1998.
- [10] W. Pan, et al., "Characterization of PAN/ATO nanocomposites prepared by solution blending". *Bulletin Materials Science*, 31, 807-11, 2008.